

Please note you will need to download this document to open hyperlinks.

Information letter for participants in non-WMO research

Information for participating in research

Environmental and climate considerations in research and innovation activities: competency profile development via a modified Delphi consensus study

Introduction

Dear Reader,

With this information letter we would like to ask you to participate in scientific research. Participation is voluntary. You are receiving this letter because you have expertise in developing training materials or coordinating training programs related to environmental and climate concerns in research and innovation for students and researchers.

Here you can read what kind of research this involves, what it means for you and what is expected of you if you decide to participate.

Are you interested?

- Please read this letter carefully.
- Ask questions of the researcher who gives you this information.

Would you like to participate? Then please tick the tick-box indicating your consent to participate at the beginning of the survey.

1. General information

The research is conducted by Amsterdam University Medical Centers as part of the RE4GREEN project.

2. What is the purpose of the research?

The RE4GREEN project aims to expand current research ethics and integrity (RE&RI) frameworks to address climate and environmental considerations in research and innovation (R&I). This aligns with the goal of achieving a just green transition in Europe, as envisaged in the European Green Deal.

Achieving this goal will require training across the R&I sector on how to adequately take into account environmental and climate considerations in R&I activities. In order to support the development of new, relevant training materials, this study aims to specify a competency profile which will be applicable to researchers, including students, early career and senior researchers, within the R&I sector.

A competency profile consists of a set of capabilities that a person needs in a certain context to function optimally in a certain role. Creating training materials and pathways around a competency profile can help ensure that training materials and pathways address specific areas of development, so that all relevant stakeholders in research and innovation can develop the skills, knowledge and attitudes to contribute to a just green transition.

In this study, we will use a modified Delphi approach to identify competencies that expert educators within the RE&RI, climate and environmental ethics, and R&I spaces agree should be in a competency profile applicable to researchers for whom training on environmental and climate considerations in R&I is relevant.

3. What happens if you participate in the study?

We have contacted you because

- 1) You coordinated a course or developed training materials that were identified via a scoping review of currently available training courses and materials which discuss environmental and climate considerations related to R&I activities;
- 2) You were recommended to us by a member of the RE4GREEN consortium;
- 3) Your profile was identified as relevant by one of the research team, or
- 4) You responded to our call for participation.

If you agree to participate, you will be invited to a maximum of three rounds of a questionnaire formed of open and closed questions aimed at reaching consensus on which items to include in a competency profile. The questionnaires will take approximately 30-45 minutes to complete. We will also ask you some socio-demographic characteristics in the questionnaire, such as: affiliation

(including country of work); gender; area of expertise (field/discipline); specific expertise training researchers (courses coordinated).

Tools

Delphi questionnaire responses we will be gathered using LimeSurvey.

Burdens

Taking part in this study requires a time commitment. For each round of the Delphi study, we estimate that the questionnaire will take 30-45 minutes to complete. In other words, a time commitment of roughly 60-90 minutes can be expected between February and May 2025.

4. What does participation mean for you?

There is no direct benefit to you as a participant of this study. However, your participation and expertise will contribute to a competence profile which will be used for the development of new open access training materials and tailored training pathways which will support yourself and others within your field of work. Please also take into account the aforementioned time costs.

5. If you do not want to participate, or want to stop the study.

Participation in the study is completely voluntary. You may also decide to stop during the research. You don't have to say why you're quitting. However, you must report this immediately to the coordinating researcher. You may also ask that your personal data are deleted from our database of experts.

Please note that if you decide to withdraw from the study after your questionnaire responses have been analysed it will no longer be possible to remove your responses, so the data collected up to that point will be used for the research.

6. What do we do with your data?

Will you participate in the research? Then you also give permission to collect, use and store your data.

Why do we collect, use and store your data?

We collect, use and store your data to answer the research questions in this study. We also intend to publish the results of the research.

How do we protect your privacy?

The Delphi process will take place online, and will consist of 2 or, depending on how the process unfolds, 3 questionnaire rounds. Your written responses will be collected, analysed and shared with other participants in pseudonymized, aggregated form. No identifiable data will be shared at any time.

To protect your privacy, we give your data a code. We only put this code (not any personal identifiable data) on all of your questionnaire responses or interview transcripts. The data that refers directly to you will then no longer be used. Only the researcher and members of the AMC research team know which code you have (the key is not shared with consortium partners). When we process or share your data, we always use only that code. In reports and publications about the research, no one will be able to link your responses back to you.

You will have the opportunity to grant permission for your name and affiliation to be shared in the final publication associated with this work. We will contact you at a later date and seek separate explicit permission for this (you are not obliged to agree and may choose to remain anonymous).

How long do we keep your data?

We store your data for 5 years (until completion of the RE4GREEN project) in the online file system of the research centre.

Can you withdraw your consent to the use of your data?

You may leave the study, withdraw your consent to the use of your data and request that your associated data is deleted, at any time without providing a reason. This applies to the use in this study and to the use in other research. But, if you withdraw your consent after your questionnaire responses have been analysed it will no longer be possible to remove your responses, so the data collected up to that point will be used for the research.

After this investigation, may we contact you again for a follow-up investigation?

When this investigation is over, we plan to do follow-up research relating to the piloting and implementation of the training materials that will be developed based on our findings from this study. We would then like to contact you and ask whether you would like to participate again. You can indicate on the consent form whether you give us permission for this.

Would you like to know more about your privacy?

You may wish to receive an electronic copy of your data that was used for the research (Delphi questionnaire responses). This is possible. You can ask the researcher about this. Would you like to

know more about your rights when processing personal data? Then look up <https://www.autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/nl/over-privacy/persoonsgegevens>

Do you have questions about your rights? Or do you have a complaint about your privacy? Please contact Natalie Evans (contact details below).

Where can you find more information about the research?

You will find more information about the research on the following website:

<https://re4green.eu/>

7. Do you have any questions?

This research was assessed by the non-WMO review committee of the Amsterdam UMC. According to this committee, this research does not fall under the Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act (WMO). If you have any questions about this study, please contact the research team.

8. Do you have a complaint?

If you have any complaints about your privacy, we recommend that you first discuss these with the research team. You can also go to the Data Protection Officer of Amsterdam University Medical Centers who can be contacted via privacy@amsterdamumc.nl. Or you can file a complaint with the Dutch Data Protection Authority using the following URL: <https://autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/>

Thank you for your attention.

Main Researchers contact details:

Natalie Evans

Associate Professor

Department of Ethics, Law and Humanities

Amsterdam University Medical Centers

n.evans@amsterdamumc.nl

Lucy Sabin

Postdoctoral Researcher

Department of Ethics, Law and Humanities

Amsterdam University Medical Centers

l.r.sabin@amsterdamumc.nl

